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Recruitment And Organisational Productivity In Rivers State Civil Service, 2013-2023

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ABSTRACT

Rivers state civil service implements governmental policies and development programmes. This paper examines staff recruitment's effect on organizational productivity. It utilized equity theory and a mixed research method. Data includes quantitative and qualitative data from interviews. The main recruitment methods were internal and external, with more reliance on the external method. Findings revealed that Organizational need assessment was neglected before recruitment. Ethnicity undermines meritocracy and competence in civil service employment. The paper recommends using internal methods more than external ones and placing emphasis on knowledge, skill, and competence for recruitment.

Keywords: Civil Service, Civil Service Commission, Recruitment, Rivers State, Productivity

INTRODUCTION

The Civil Service in Nigeria is the creation of the colonial masters. Britain bequeathed the model of Civil Service to Nigeria that was narrow in structure and objectives. It was organized in a way that enabled colonial masters to efficaciously withdraw the highly coveted financial and material resources needed by their controlling metropolitan powers. In 1960, when Nigerian nationalist took over the administrative leadership, no effort was made by them to modify the Civil Service to fit in our own developmental needs. The Nigeria bureaucrats who occupied the leadership position in the Civil Service imbibed the colonial mentality of wealth acquisition for self-discouragement and self-superiority rather than working to make better the lot of the country, they became colonial masters in a, "black man's skin", this aggravated the poor performance of the Civil Service and consequently caused the under development of the country. In an attempt to reduce the deterioration happening in the civil service, almost all post-independence government took some measures to reform or improve the skills and overall performance of the civil service, because scholars like Mustapha and Omorede (2017) believe that the ability of a nation's development rests on the capacity of its civil service. In a bid to further develop the civil service system of Nigeria, the service had over the years been subjected to several reforms. The Udoji reform of 1972 emphasized on the need for public review commission organization, structure and management; recruitment and conditions of employment, pensions and superannuation; regarding of all post and review of salaries; introduction of result-oriented management in the public service (Maduabum, 2008). The Ayida panel also stressed on the need for recruitment into the civil service especially at the entry grades of professional cadres to be based on merit and federal character and not on the spoil system.

Recruitment is the process of discovering and catching qualified or appropriate applicant to fill the vacant position. Recruitment for any organization is very important right through the life span of that

organization (Alwi ,Hasan, & Zaman, 2022; Barrah, 2020; Dan, Ayodele, & Abiodun, 2020; Dominic, & Peter, 2019). This is why government from to time do recruit and offer appointments to prospective candidates to fill in the vacant positions with a view to keeping the government’s work going (Mugambi, & Omuya; Oyadiran, Ishaq, & Kola., 2023; Gold, & Bratton, 2021). Recruitment is government tool for increasing the workforce by hiring candidates with the right qualification, attitude and enthusiasm to demonstrate commitment on the job and enhance productivity.

Productivity is said to be the quantity produced and participation over a given period of time and with rapt attention given to quality and efficient use of all resources (Anosa, 2021; Dickson, Achanya, & Andeline; Inyang, 2019). Productivity is doing the right thing, the right way, getting more output with less input, getting more output from the same input, speed level, removing waste in all its forms, justifying wages, improving all aspects of life, producing better and better quality (The national productivity centre in fact book, 2015).

Karimi, Teimouri, Shahin and Barzoki (2019), the survival and productivity of any organization is evident on its human factors and for any organization to carryout activities geared towards the attainment of its pre-targeted goals, the emphasis is laid on the types of workforce available and the process of having efficient and effective workforce does happen through an effective recruitment and selection process. A competent and effective civic service workforce requires a systematic and transparent recruitment and selection process.

However, this study is centred on Rivers state civil service which is the body of professional civil servants entrusted with the responsibility of carrying out the policies of the Rivers State government in relation to infrastructural development and social service delivery. Certain core values exist within the civil service which all civil servants are expected to share and uphold. These core values are integrity, meritocracy, discipline, professionalism, patriotism, impartiality and secrecy of government information, except where the information divulged conforms to the Freedom of Information Act (FOI). To keep the civil servant successful in Rivers state, there is need to constantly take measures of productivity improvement and in other to improve, there is need to know what exactly needs to be done.

So far, existing literature has investigated the extent of recruitment and organizational productivity in the civic service; Obichere and Onuoha (2019), examined the relationship between balanced scorecard and employee productivity of civil servants in Rivers State, Nigeria. Usulor (2020) interrogated staffing process and employees’ service delivery: A study of Ebonyi state civil service system, among others. However, it is not yet evident in literature the extent of recruitment of civil servant in Rivers state civil service and if it has enhanced the quality of workforce and efficiency in the state civil service. This paper therefore has its thrust, recruitment and organisational productivity in Rivers State Civil Service, 2013 to 2023. To achieve this, the paper poses a question, thus: “What are the existing methods of recruitment in Rivers State Civil Service?”

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Equity Theory

Stacy Adams (1965), the chief proponent of equity theory focuses on a person’s perception of fairness with respect to a relationship. It holds that the motivating factor workers desire is hinged on the inputs and outcomes ratio from their job situation and then compared with the same inputs- outcomes ratio of those of relevant others. The term equity connotes with the concepts of fairness and equal treatment in comparison to people who behave in similar ways (Sapru, 2013).

According to Williams (2003), ‘Adams equity theory is based on the propositions of the fair balance between inputs and outputs among workers to ensure maximum job performance. The organization must ensure that the workers who perform well are appropriately rewarded to sustain and eventually, increase their job performance’. The workers continuously seek to maximize their pay, which in this case, the pay is deemed as reward without the inclusion of cost. A person’s perception of equity develops through a three- step process as shown below:

- i. First an individual evaluates the way he is being treated by an organization.
- ii. The next step is for an individual to choose a co-worker who seems to be in a roughly similar situation and to observe how an organization treats him.

iii. In the crucial step of equity theory an individual ‘compares’ the two treatments seem similar or if they are different.

What this theory states is that staff in different organizations constantly evaluate their level of effort against fellow staff and the reward they receive for their effort. If they sense that there is a significant difference between their level of effort and reward with that of their fellow staff, they will endeavor to bring about equality of effort for everyone by adjusting up or down their own performance or by taking measure to adjust the level of their fellow workers. Likewise, the relative reward for effect is also monitored.

Equity theory stipulates that:

Inputs: Inputs include all the rich and diverse elements that employees believe they bring or contribute to the job – their education, experience, effort, loyalty, commitment

Outcomes: Outcomes are rewards they perceive they get from their jobs and employers outcomes include- direct pay and bonuses, fringe benefit, job security, social rewards and psychological.

Over rewarded: If employees feel over-rewarded equity theory predicts then they will feel an imbalance in their relationship with their employees and seek to restore that balance.

Equity: If employees perceive equity, then they will be motivated to continue to contribute act about the same level.

Unrewarded: employees who feel they have been unrewarded and seek to reduce their feeling in equity through the same types of strategies but some of this specific action are now reverse.

The essential aspects of the equity theory may be shown by an equation; there should be a balance of the outcomes/inputs relationship for one person in comparison with that for another person. If the person thinks that the rewards are greater than what is considered, he/she may work harder. If the person perceives the rewards as equitable, he/she probably will continue at the same level of output. If the person feels that he/she is inequitably rewarded, he/she may be dissatisfied, reduce the quantity or quality of output, or even leave the organization.

Figure 2.1: The three situations of equity theory.

Source: Adams (1965)

Equity theory demonstrates that, for most employees, motivation is influenced significantly by relative rewards as well as by absolute rewards, but some key issues are still unclear. The goal is to ensure employees are rewarded equitably.

Equity theory can be a useful framework of analysis on issues bothering on fairness in recruitment and organization productivity in the Rivers State Civil Service. According to the principles of the Equity theory, the best recruitment and selection criteria in the organization is that which is based on

the principles of fairness and equal treatment in comparison to others. Civil servants perceive what they get in terms of promotion and salary in relation to their educational qualification and competency and then compare it to the output; salary and promotion and input; education and competency of employee in other related organization. When they feel that what the other employee receives in relation to the input and output ratio is equal to theirs, they feel that there is equality, fairness and justice but when the reverse is the case, they feel under rewarded or over rewarded which can affect productivity negatively or positively. Findings revealed that fairness in recruitment promotes the hiring of competent staff, the performance of civil servants are influenced by the quality of its employees, and equal treatment gets them motivated in the workplace because lack of workplace motivation is one of the major issues impeding excellent service performance in the Nigerian civil service.

The relevance of Equity theory to this study is that, civil servants will only work efficiently when they feel that, the government is being fair to them and also practices equity, fairness and justice. This is capable of improving their job satisfaction leading to efficient service delivery and high productivity.

THE RIVERS STATE CIVIL SERVICE COMMISSION

The Rivers State Civil Service Commission was handed down by the then Eastern Nigeria Administration. The Commission was championed by the Military Governors of the old Rivers State; Commander Alfred Diette-Spiff, Lt. Col. Zamani Lekwot, Navy Commander Suleiman Saidu. In 1979, the Commission transited into the Government of the first civilian administration; Late Chief Melford Okilo. Iroanwusi (2015) posits that under Okilo's regime, the Rivers State Civil Service Commission reached its water-mark which includes performance, achievement, and credibility.

The top echelon of the Commission was central to the government at that time, as the Secretaries to the Military Government, Commissions or Administrative Committees of Inquiries, Divisional Officers and Sole Administrators of Local Governments were appointed from the Administrative class of the Service. Even professional officers like Education Officers, Agricultural and Fisheries Officers, all kinds of Engineers, Law Officers and Technical Officers were appointed from the Service into Ministries (Iroanwusi, 2015). Iroanwusi, (2015), revealed that the Commission from 1967 to 1991 was a Golden era for the Service opining that "the ethos and nuances of the Service were strictly observed by all and sundry. The Service could lift its head high and compete favourably with all other Services of the Federation within this period. This was "the period when monumental infrastructural achievements were made in the State. Morale of officers and staffs were high, with low financial remunerations as obtained then, civil servants were willing to perform their duties".

The Rivers State Civil Service began to suffer setbacks during the General Ibrahim Babangida regime constituted the Dotun Philips Committee to restructure the Civil Service. Part of the recommendation of the Committee was for the Permanent Secretary of the Commissions to grow to the position of Director-General and should retire with the government that appointed them. This recommendation was adopted and enshrined by the promulgation of the Civil Service Reform Decree 43 of 1988. Iroanwusi (2015) believed that this Decree major achievement was to politicise the position of the Permanent Secretary. Making the civil service lose its virtue of being dedicated, experienced, and hard-working officer who are forcefully retired from the Service without attaining the mandatory sixty (60) years of age or thirty of service. The Decree personalised professionals into the Civil Service, by removing the Administrative Cadre from the Service; provided that the Directorate grade and stipulated that officers from the professional grades could be appointed as Permanent Secretaries. Iroanwusi (2015) considered this as a way of robbing the Administration Class of its privilege.

The function and administration of the civil service is not a loosed one. Every organisation that exists comes under control of a body that acts as the key administrator. The civil service is controlled under a commission that directs and presents the goals and objective of the service. Firstly, a commission is a body that has been delegated power of control of a particular political parastatal or bureau in accordance with the policies of the government in power. Hence, in this sense, the civil service commission that the government has delegated the control and administration of the entirety of the role and function of the civil service. To a large extent, they assume the recruitment of citizens into the civil service and also fire who ever does not meet the needs or fails to carry out the policies of the commission.

The policies of the commission is mostly generated by the executive arm of government that is according to statute is the body that implement the policies and laws of state, they are the chief administrators of any government and therefore, they are fully represented by the civil service commission that function as the most significant part of public administration. Most countries have different nomenclature used to describe the civil service commission. In Nigeria, the civil service commission is modeled in a broad scale, as states in Nigeria have their distinct commission that is employed and controlled by the state executive body. At the centre, The Federal Civil Service Commission is the body established by the executive body in Nigeria to appoint and transfers, and to carry out disciplinary control over all Federal Civil Servants. At the State, we have the various civil service commissions that head the activities of civil servants and civil services generally.

The Rivers State Civil Service Commission is the statutorily executive body powered to control and oversee the activities and administration of the state's civil service. The Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria (As Amended) Part II, section 197 (1), under the Third Schedule empowers: "A State Civil Service Commission shall comprise the following members: - A Chairman; Not less than two and not more than four other persons, who shall, in the opinion of the Governor, be persons of unquestionable integrity and sound political judgment. Therefore, the constitution of Nigeria causes the Rivers State Civil Service Commission to exist in order to perform the same function the Federal Civil Service Commission at the federal level. In this view, the commission in Rivers State perform the function of appoint, discipline and fire persons holding or acting in offices within the civil service of various ministries and department in the State. The Chairman of the Commission is appointed by the Governor of the State with the approval of the State House of Assembly. The modus operandi of the Commission is stated clearly on the website of the Commission cited by careernews.com.ng (2020) another:

The Rivers State Civil Service Commission (RSCS) is the body of professional civil servants entrusted with the responsibility of carrying out the policies of the Rivers State government in relation to infrastructural development and social service delivery. Certain core values exist within the civil service which all civil servants are expected to share and uphold. These core values are integrity, meritocracy, discipline, professionalism, patriotism, impartiality and secrecy of government information, except where the information divulged conforms to the Freedom of Information Act (FOI). The body is led by the Head of Service (HOS), a member of the executive council, who is the most senior administrative official within the civil service of Rivers State. The civil servants are found mainly in the ministries and parastatals, where they perform their duties, progressing based on qualifications and seniority. The ministries are managed by Permanent Secretaries who report to Commissioners in the executive council.

The Rivers State Civil Service Commission administers over the civil service of the ministries in the State and the Ministries have departments and agencies. The Rivers State Commission oversees the 26 Ministries in the State. According to the 2011 & 2012 Reports of the Rivers State Civil Service Commission, revealed that The Commission like its counterparts in the Federation relies on the provision of the Public Service Rules (PSR), the Financial Regulations (FR), Establishment Circulars, the Scheme of Service and other relevant service documents to carry out its statutory functions. Hence, the Commission performs such functions as:

- i. carrying out appointment; promotions/advancements; confirmation of appointment; transfers, integration, Discipline, secondments, reinstatements, conversions and retirements of staff;
- ii. Monitoring the activities of Ministries/Extra-Ministerial Departments in order to ensure that the rules, regulations and other guidelines are strictly and uniformly adhered to;
- iii. Attending meetings of Departmental Selection Board of all Ministries and Extra-Ministerial Departments, reviewing and ratifying decisions of the Departmental Selection Boards from grade level 01-06 before implementation;
- iv. Serving as an appellate body for all Appeals and Petitions in the Civil Service;

- v. Maintaining a comprehensive and up-to-date personnel record for the Civil Service and gazetting all cases of the Commission;
- vi. Coordinating Federal Civil Service Recruitment Interviews in Rivers State;
- vii. Production of Annual Reports;
- viii. Taking part in Annual Conferences organised by the Federal Civil Service Commission (Conference of Civil Service Commission) of Nigeria.

The Commission is fashioned to perform these functions as an appellate body totally free according to the Constitutional provision which states inter-alias that in exercising its powers the Civil Service Commission shall not be subject to the direction and control of any other authority or power. The Commission is also expected to be transparent especially when it comes to petitions from Ministries and extra-ministerial departments submitted to them. The Commission convened to carry out most important functions especially when issues before the Commission were to be discussed and policies and decisions of the Commission were to be formulated and implemented, these meetings includes: regular meetings, emergency meetings; individual members processing matters under the schedule; circulating files to each Members for the inputs before final decisions are taken.

There are certain core values that exist within the Rivers State Civil Service which all Civil Servants are expected to obey and uphold. These core values are integrity, meritocracy, discipline, professionalism, patriotism, impartiality and secrecy of government information except where the information divulged conforms with the Freedom of Information Act. The Rivers State Civil Service is founded on ethical principles- work ethics to which every organisational member must comply with.

It is obvious that the Commission is a structured and patterned organisation with clear cut definition of roles and function. It is clear that the Commission shares vertical powers and communication patterns that flows from the Chairman; who is the Head of the Commission, next to the four Commissioners of the Commission down to Permanent Secretary who directs the four Directors. Hence, the Commission is made up four major departments viz: Administration; Planning, Research and Statistics; Appeals and Petitions; Finance and Supplies

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The chapter presents the data analysis and interpretation for the study. The data collected were based on the research questions formulated to guide the study as follows:

Table 1 Questionnaire Return Report

Detail	Frequency	Percentage
Administered Questionnaire	400	100%
Returned/relevant questionnaires	394	98.4%
Unreturned/irrelevant questionnaires	6	1.6%

Source: Field Study, 2024.

Table 1 shows the percentage of questionnaires returned. 400 questionnaires were administered to the respondents, out of which 394 questionnaires were returned found relevant while 6 questionnaires indicating 1.6% were found not relevant.

Table 2 Bio-data of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Marital Status	Male	219	55.6
	Female	175	44.4
	Married	241	61.2
	Singles	98	24.9
Age	Separated/Divorced	55	14.0
	20-30 years	44	11.2
	31-40 years	44	11.2
	41-50 years	174	44.2
	51-60 years	88	22.3
Educ. Qualification	60 years and Above	44	11.2
	SSCE/OND	88	22.3
	HND/B.Sc	87	22.1
	M.Sc/M.A	131	33.2
	Ph.D	88	22.3
Years in Service	Less than 10 years	89	22.6
	11-20 years	83	21.1
	21-30 years	183	46.4
	Greater than 30 years	39	9.9
Total		394	100%

Source: Field Study, 2024.

Table 2 presents the bio-data of the respondents, categorised by gender, marital status, age, educational qualifications, and years in service, with a total of 394 respondents, indicating a 100% response rate. The gender distribution is male (219 individuals, 55.6%) and female (175 individuals, 44.4). The study had more male than female respondents. The data shows that the majority of the respondents are married, with 241 people married at 61.2%, followed by the single respondents at 98 (24.9%) and lastly 55 (14%) separated or divorced respondents. The age range for the data is 20-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years, 51-60 years, and 60 years and above. The individual has a strong academic background, including a degree in SSCE/OND, HND/B.Sc, M.Sc/M.A, and Ph.D. The number of years in service varies from less than 10 years (89), 11-20 years (83), 21-30 years (183), and more than 30 years (39).

Question: *What are the existing methods of recruitments in Rivers State Civil Service?*

Table 3: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation on Existing Methods of Recruitment in Rivers State Civil Service.

S/N	What are the existing methods of recruitments in the rivers state civil service?	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD	Remark
1.	Internal recruitment through transfer of service.	186	178	55	75	2.95	1.17	Accepted
2.	Internal recruitment through promotion from within the service and job rotation	66	135	94	99	2.43	1.04	Rejected
3.	Internal recruitment through conversion of support staff	151	84	84	75	2.79	1.15	Accepted
4.	External recruitment through public advertisement	115	194	42	42	2.97	0.91	Accepted
5.	Every employee goes through a competitive transparent and credible selection process	18	77	75	224	1.72	0.63	Accepted
Grand mean						2.57	0.98	Accepted

Source: Field Study, 2024.

Table 3 above showed the existing methods of recruitment in the Rivers State Civil Service. The table indicated with (\bar{x} =2.95, std, 1.17) that internal recruitment through transfer of service is an existing method of recruitment in Rivers State Civil Service. The result of data with (\bar{x} = 2.43, std 1.04) however rejected the view that promotion from within the service and job rotation is an existing method of recruitment in the service. The result of the data presented with (\bar{x} = 2, 79, std. 1.15) accepted that conversion of support staff is an internal recruitment method in Rivers State Civil Service. There was also indication that external recruitment through public advertisement was another method of recruitment into the service. This got a mean score (\bar{x} = 2.97, std. 0-91) and was therefore accepted. Finally on table 4.3, the data showed with (\bar{x} = 1. 72, std. 0. 63) that every employee in the Rivers State Civil Service did not go through a competitive, transparent and credible selection process.

The indication of the result above was that with a grand mean (\bar{x} = 2.57, std 0.98) which was above the criterion mean (\bar{x} = 2.5), the respondents accepted that internal recruitment through transfer of service, internal recruitment through a conversation of support staff and external recruitment through public advertisement were generally the dominant existing recruitment methods in the Rivers State Civil Service. They however negated the view that promotions from within the service and job rotation were recruitment methods in the service.

The result of the oral interview supported the result of the quantitative existing method of recruitment in the Rivers State Civil Service. One of the interviewees, Mr. Princewill Nweke, a Deputy Director revealed thus:

There are two methods of recruitment namely: internal and external methods. He went further to explain the two methods, for him internal method is when they decide to fill up the vacant positions using people who are already in the system, for example the support staff. While the external method begins with the advertisement in print media, electronic devices and social media. The method begins with advertorial, receiving of applications, conducting of interviews, selection and giving of appointment letters to successful applicants, posting and deployment to various departments, (Nweke, Personal communication, 10 March, 2024).

In another interview with a staff of the Rivers State Civil Service Commission Mr. Felix Amadi, further added:

Recruitment is done by both the Rivers state civil service commission and the Departmental selection board (DSB). The former is responsible for the recruitment of graduates from grade level 07 – 17 while the latter is responsible for the recruitment of non- graduates from grade level 01-06. He stated further that the DSB is made up of all heads of department within the ministry and they are in charge of transfer, promotion, discipline, compensation, benefits motivation and retirement of the civil servant under their care. (Amadi, 10 March, 2024).

Quite interestingly the respondent objected that all employees in the service went through competitive, transparent and credible selection process. This would imply that other factors considered were in the recruitment exercise such factors were considered in the next analysis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Existing Recruitment Methods in Rivers State Civil Service

From the data presented and analysed, the study found internal and external recruitment as the dominant recruitment methods deployed by the Rivers State Civil Service Commission to recruit staff of the Rivers State Civil Service. Such internal recruitment methods being deployed within the period under review were through the conversion of support staff otherwise described by the Public Service Rule as non-personable contract employee. The civil service also uses the method of external advertisement to recruit persons to fill existing vacancies. It is expected that all staff employed through the external recruitment method must go through a competitive, transparent and credible

selection process. However, the data presented and analysed, particularly in response to questionnaire item no. 5 showed that such laid down procedure has not been followed in the recruitment process. There are indications that other factors have negatively influenced the recruitment into the Rivers State Service. Attention is given to these factors somewhere in this section of the study.

The quantitative data from the interview threw light on the internal recruitment method. It showed that internal recruitment allowed the system to fill existing vacancies with person already in the system offering same services as required by that position as a support (non-personable contract) staff. One advantage of this method is that the employee had acquired some of the requisite skills, knowledge and attitude required for such position. The employee would have also developed high altitude to organizational commitment. Such employee is not coming as a green horn requiring training and orientation to fit into the system. This form of recruitment is less expensive, less cumbersome. However, it has its demerit. Such demerit is that the general challenges facing recruitment in Nigeria such as ethnicity, cronyism also undermines its effectiveness.

The external recruitment while it is open and also provides opportunity for inclusivity appears to be a cumbersome process with many internal loopholes and contradictions. Examples of recruitment analysed; Electrical, Mechanical and Waste Engineers and Clerical Staff (2013), Experienced Surveyors, Medical Officers, Accountants and Auditors and Administrative Staff (2016), State Counsels (2018) and Doctors and Nurses (2018), Medical Officers (2021).

It takes a lot of time and resources. Many times, the process is open to abuse and manipulation. This could be one of the rationales behind outsourcing in the recruitment processes in some circumstances. The outsourcing of the recruitment process, from screening to interview and short-listing of successful candidate as employee is done by professional human resource management firm, with high ethical standard and love of conduct.

Meanwhile, internal recruitment through promotion from within the service and job rotation showed up as another viable method. But it equally has its lacuna. Firstly its advantage lies also in providing dedicated and committed manpower. Secondly, such manpower does not require much training for his new role. This is because his/her selection was on based on observed competence in the expected role. It has the tendency of producing persons who can fit into the job and enhance productivity. However, this method together with the method of conversion of casual (non-personable) employee may not be able to sufficiently supply the required number of manpower at a given time (particularly in case of mass vacancies). This method may be good for the higher educational system where self-reproduction is importance. It is however not very favourable to the civil service.

In all, this finding corroborates the findings of Briggs (2008) which held that the two method of recruitment readily available or existing in the civil are internal recruitment and external recruitment. The present study had however ever gone ahead to state the merits and demerits of each of the methods.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The Nigeria public sector is facing poor service delivery due to lack of transparency in the recruitment process. Innovative human resource management practices can help organisations develop and renew capabilities, recruitment process is marred with irregularities, often hiring incompetent individuals based on political affinity or high-profile recommendations. This lack of merit contributes to socio-economic problems and underperformance. This study aimed at investigating the recruitment status, its impact, and the linkage on organisational productivity of the Rivers State Civil Service. The study showed that the recruitment methods in Rivers State Civil Service includes internal and external recruitment. According to the study, Internal recruitment make use of existing employees to fill up vacant position, while the external recruitment begins with the advertorial, receiving of applications, conducting of interviews, selection and giving of appointment letters to successful applicants, posting and deployment to various departments. That there are two main methods of recruitment namely, internal and external recruitment. According to the study, Internal recruitment make use of existing employees to fill up vacant position, while the external recruitment begins with the advertorial, receiving of applications, conducting of interviews, selection and giving of appointment letters to successful applicants, posting and deployment to various departments;

Also, by the analysis of table presented above the result showed that recruitment method had not impacted positively on organisational productivity of the civil service such: that quality of manpower has not enhanced effective service delivery; absent of massive regular recruitment has not provided the civil with the required manpower hence performance of the civil servant has not enhanced the operation of government, service delivery and organisational productivity. The null hypothesis was rejected, meaning that there is a negative significant relationship between the impact of recruitment method on the organisational productivity of the Rivers State Civil Service, 2013- 29023.

Based on the fore - going, the following recommendations suggested for effective recruitment and organisational productivity in Rivers state:

- 1) The Government of Rivers State through the instrumentality of the Civil Service Commission should make use of the internal methods of recruitment more than the external method because the internal method helps to absorb tested and proven staff. Unlike the external recruitment methods that brings in freshers and inexperienced people that may not be willing to work. The support staff in the various ministries and department should not be made to wait until there is a formal recruitment exercise, they should be converted ones they are certified fit for the position
- 2) The Rivers State Government should place greater emphasis on knowledge, skill (particularly ICT skills and knowledge) and competence as basic criteria for recruitment into the civil service. But the commission must ensure that the best brains are gotten using this factors. There should be consideration of merit in recruitment instead of primordial factors of friendship and relationship. This will undoubtedly facilitate a pool of competent workers in the industry, resulting in good performance outcomes.

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